

IN THE SOCIAL STRUCTURE OF YOUTH SOCIETY OPPORTUNITIES AND TASKS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5998610>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 01st February 2022

Accepted: 05th February 2022

Online: 10th February 2022

KEY WORDS

*youth, society, state,
development strategy, social
structure, potential.*

ABSTRACT

The article analyzes the role of youth in the social structure of society, the development strategy reflects the interests of young people, draws conclusions and recommendations.

The development of the homeland depends, first of all, on the maturity of its children. The announcement of this year by the head of state as the Year of Human Dignity and Active Community has laid the foundation for making young people the decisive force in our lives today and tomorrow, laying the foundation for their worthy place in society and expanding the field for youth self-expression.

Talented, active and high-potential young people have always been the driving force of every society. Their aspirations and feedback are one of the key factors in determining the changes that are taking place in life, the reforms that are taking place. Ensuring the active participation of young people in the political and economic processes of the country is of great importance.

Today, 64% of the population is under 30 years old. From the first days of independence, our people have been determined to build a new life, a new society, to build our future as an integral part of the world community. The developed programs, with all their essence and significance, are an important condition for achieving such lofty goals - a very important and necessary activity in raising a healthy and harmoniously developed generation with independent thinking, strong will, deep knowledge, no less than anyone else. In order to not only express confidence in young people, but also to express themselves in practice, it is necessary to raise their political and legal culture, develop their democratic skills and be educated in the spirit of devotion to our national idea.

Today in our country all the conditions are created for young people to get an education, to learn the secrets of the profession and craft. There is also a constant focus on supporting gifted and talented young people. The work done in this direction in the higher education system is noteworthy. In the past, pedagogy in the provinces seemed to have no higher education institutions other than higher education institutions. There are currently 159 higher education institutions. In other words, higher education is moving directly to our regions, cities and districts. In addition, new higher education institutions were built at the request of the period. The University of World Economy and Diplomacy, which is tasked with training international economists and diplomats, as well as the International Islamic Academies of Uzbekistan, which train specialists in Islamic religion and legal education, have been established.

Over the past years, the Law "On Education" and the National Program of Personnel Training have been adopted in order to radically reform the education system, bring it up to modern standards, build a new system of national training, and educate a harmonious and talented generation for the future. The implementation of the requirements of the Law and the Program has been identified as a priority of public policy and is carried out in three stages in a logical manner. Indeed, modern conditions are being created for the education of our youth, and they are being encouraged both materially and spiritually. To date, our young people are educated in modernly built beautiful buildings, classrooms equipped with the most modern visual aids, reading rooms. They are

mastering modern knowledge and technology.

What the reform of the education system has given us: Young people have modern knowledge, their minds and worldviews have changed, and most importantly, young people have a sense of self-confidence and confidence in the future.

Today, our young people are beginning to feel that they are not indifferent to the ongoing socio-economic reforms in our country, but have a sense of belonging.

The need for education is growing among young people, the belief has been formed that I can find myself in life only if I am a qualified specialist, not a master of my profession, not for a diploma.

From the first years of independence, great attention has been paid to the training of highly qualified personnel that meet the requirements of today.

During the years of independence, all the reforms carried out in the socio-political life of our country are aimed at radically improving the interests of man and his living conditions and ensuring the active participation of our citizens in the life of the state and society. In this regard, effective work is being done to support the participation of young people in public and state affairs, to encourage them to play their part in public life.

During the years of independence, significant work has been carried out to comprehensively protect young people, support their scientific and creative activities, as well as pave the way for the management of state and public affairs. The growing role and status of young people in society is a unique feature of our country. Today, one of our main tasks is to ensure

that we, the youth, who have a new outlook and democratic thinking due to independence, will be a solid foundation for the future of our country. We, the youth, deserve the high respect shown by our state, we will contribute to the building of a

civil society if we do not waste time, use the great opportunities created for us for a positive purpose, and become educated, well-educated and selfless people for the development of our country.

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